

Potentials of sustainable Potato agriculture by precision farming in Egypt

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The agriculture sector in Egypt is one of the most important sectors, accounting for almost 15% of the national income, a value of 282 Billion EGP/Year. The sector employs more than 8.5 million person, which represent 32% of the total working labor in the country. Egypt is one of the top 20 producers of potato worldwide and the second largest producer and exporter of potatoes in Africa. Potatoes are considered the most important export vegetable crop in Egypt. More than 105000 ha are devoted for potato production, which represents about 20% of total area for vegetable production in Egypt. The total value of potato production reached 4.8 million ton/year, including 637,434 ton for exportation with a market value of 250 million USD. The potato production depends on many resources including water, energy, fertilizers, seeds ..etc. In view of the up scaling of energy crisis in Egypt and limited recourses of water, the need for proper management of the different resources became a must. Precision farming is a management technique based on optimizing the usage of different resources to maximize financial return and reduce waste. At the same time, precision farming minimizes the negative environmental impacts related to the inefficient use of agricultural inputs. In spite of potato production importance in Egypt and increasing demand for ensuring its production sustainability in order to achieve food security as well as increase a source of hard currency. Few theoretical studies addressed the importance of strategic management by precision farming in Egypt. The aim of the study is to assess the potentials of sustainable potato production using precision farming. A strategic management system for precision farming will be developed and implemented for one year - three production seasons- on a case study farm. The management system will be developed based on automated data and documentation including energy usage, water quality, soil samples, planting and harvesting practices, all data will be collected from the case study area. Several techniques will be used for the development and monitoring of this system such as remote sensing, global position system and geographic information system. At the same time preferable environmental practices based on energy, water and waste management techniques will be employed in implementing the strategic management system. Potential savings in energy, water, chemicals, seeds and fertilizers will be addressed. A cost analysis and estimated savings will be calculated. Additionally, the related impacts on potato quality, diseases and pests will be considered. Results will identify preferable practices for a strategic management system for potato production which will assist in developing management strategies for agriculture production in Egypt. Moreover, such a system will be a prototype model for implementation in similar cases as well as with different agricultural crops.

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